

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ON LANGUAGE LEARNING.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234523>

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to investigate the use of digital technologies in foreign language teaching. The importance and role of technologies is analysed in the educational process with a focus on their pros and cons, but also on the ways they are implemented in a foreign language classroom. The significant role of visualisation is also stressed, as it points at individual personality variables that need to be considered in order to prevent the emerging feelings of exhaustion and fatigue in the foreign language classroom. The particular research interest is placed around presentations as one of the crucial visual devices in the foreign language learning process. Videoconferencing is also investigated as a popular alternative in respect of their peculiarities and benefits.

Key words: technology, language learning, digital, videoconferencing, multimedia project.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since its inception, digital technology has revolutionized teaching and learning worldwide and has become an indispensable part of our daily lives. In modern society, the quality of education is affected by the teacher's performance or the educational technology or materials used in the foreign language classroom. Digital technology not only accelerates and simplifies the educational process, but also makes the learning process more interactive and cognitive. Moreover, new methods of testing and preparing such tasks could open a platform for the knowledge acquired by students to be demonstrated to the program and allow teachers to evaluate the results immediately after completing their tasks; In this way, they can take the learning process to a very high level. Therefore, the use of information technology in the learning process does not help solve all problems (passivity, bad grades, relapse, fatigue, etc.), but also in terms of perception, it directs individuals' creativity through choices. The introduction of information technology contributes to the development of different types of memory by

making students more focused and attentive. Their thoughts are not things to ponder, but things that will motivate them to take action because their reaction is as necessary as the reaction to the stimulus on the screen. It's no surprise that technology helps teaching so much.

Features such as video access, the ability to change the pace and format of learning materials, and artistic licensing make digital an essential and important part of reducing student burnout. One of the advantages of digital technology in supporting foreign language lessons is that teachers have unlimited possibilities to design their lessons as comprehensively and creatively as possible. Thanks to the good organization of the

group and independent study in the course, technological innovation leads to practical knowledge and better skills among students, making the learning process more personal as students show interest in the course. In this way, teachers develop not only the intellectual activity of their students but also their creative skills. While considering all the benefits of digital technology, we should not forget that excessive and incorrect use can also harm the learning process. Although technology plays an important role in education, it should be well integrated into the educational process and used with new learning methods. The introduction of digital technology in foreign language education has its own character, but it also arises from the teacher's ability to choose the best teaching strategies and digital methods, which also affects the level of success of students in their lessons. Depending on the objectives and selected teaching strategies, CDs, DVDs, cameras, computers, internet, tablets, phones, etc. will help students in the lesson. There are different learning tools.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Literature review

The issue of the application of digital technologies in education has been discussed for many years not only at Russian conferences, but also at foreign language conferences: "International Conference on Educational Technologies and Computers" (England, 2009), "Development of Information Technologies in Education: Use of New Educational Materials in Education" (Tomsk, 2010), "New Information Technologies in Education" (Ekaterinburg, 2014) etc. and B. Dendev (Moscow, 2013), Teaching English as a Second Language with ICT Adams & Brindley (United Kingdom, 2007), in Foreign Language Teaching New Approaches (Methods, Evaluation and Innovation), Lopes and Ruiz Cecilia (United Kingdom, 2018), Learning in Blended English Language Teaching: Planning Lessons and Practice, Tomlinson and Whittaker (United Kingdom, 2013),

Research Methods in Education by Sohen, Louis, Manion, Lawrence and Morrison, Keith (England, 2010) and other journals such as Journal of Information Technology for Teachers, Higher Education in Europe, Learning, Media and Technology, Technology, Teaching and Learning, Journal of Educational Leadership, Quarterly Review of Distance Education, UK Journal of Educational Technology and others.

2.2. Visualisation

Visual arts have a special place in the learning process. Visualization is the process of presenting information using visuals, and its purpose is to reduce ease of understanding; The visual form can be anything you can think of, a lesson, a process, etc. Can be used for. Jan Comenius, one of the first scientists to draw attention to the principle of visualization in education, emphasized that it is one of the most important tools in education. learning process. The importance of watching visuals was also emphasized by another Russian teacher, Ushinskij, who said that it is a tool that reveals the individual characteristics of students. Ushinskij emphasized that visualization makes learning easier, more specific, and more fun, thus avoiding the feeling of failure and fatigue (27). Therefore, the use of computers in the educational process opens new ways of developing ideas that provide new opportunities for effective learning.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Presentation and her options

One of the most important aspects of applying technology in English lessons is project activities. Many discussions are part of the learning process, and students use the Internet to gather resources. The method used to collect and interpret new information is called the integration method. We can teach foreign language lessons by preparing different types of presentations. Typically, the examination of a topic or chapter ends with a combination of items. All of this can be combined by inviting students to create a multimedia project at the end of each topic. It is worth noting that the students were quite willing to give a large number of presentations. This is another way to develop students' interest in learning languages. The best outcome of using lectures is the fast pace of the course, students' interest and self-expression.

3.2. Videoconferencing as a presentation tool nowadays

Considering that limited study opportunities outside the classroom have now brought us to another level in foreign language teaching, the main aim of improving students' skills is the use of new technologies, especially the new audio and video communication technologies that have emerged recently. In the field of

education, they have become important factors in achieving success in foreign language courses. According to Canale and Swain, achieving this communication goal will enhance the development of communication skills [2], [3] was based on the following areas of knowledge and skills: grammar, sociolinguistics, practical strategies and conversation skills.

4. CONCLUSION

The role of digital technology in foreign language teaching has been one of the most discussed topics at conferences not only in Russia but also in the UK and has been published in various publications. Visual components play an important role in the application of digital technologies in education, and therefore visualization plays an important role in education in various forms, from full-time schools to distance education. Visualization is closely linked to distance learning or self-learning, where various simulation methods are available aimed at developing speaking skills and critical thinking, in which the teacher acts not as a guide, but as an educator. Discussions are the most frequently used tools in the development of images and contribute to the creation of new, original ideas, the promotion of artistic ideas and the improvement of the level of technical reception and production. Productive skills and analytical skills can be developed using a variety of programs such as E-lektif, Text adapter, or Live-ink software, which makes foreign language texts understandable to students through visual integration. Moreover, the current situation surrounding the Covid-19 virus, which has greatly affected the way teachers work around the world, has also affected teaching and has become a visible reality, forces many teachers and professors to deal with the work of many modern programs such as: , Zoom, Loom, etc. allowing them to teach students using stress-reducing strategies. . These apps not only allow teachers and professors to give feedback to their students, but also provide students with a unique opportunity to interact with other students, regardless of their location. Both students and teachers can share their discussions, and unlike the face-to-face model, video lessons reduce students' poor behavior and increase their willingness to communicate, bridging long distances and developing their communication skills to the fullest. . .

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayeva, G. (2022). LEARNERS' PSYCHOLOGY AS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES INFLUENCING LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 11(11). http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/download/6321/40

2. Abdullayeva, G. G. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 555-560. <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/520>
3. Abdullayeva, G. G. . (2023). Ways of Motivating Young Learners in EFL Classroom. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 122–124. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1109>
4. C. Kinginger, Videoconferencing as access to spoken French. Modern Language Journal 82 (1998) 502– 513.
5. Gaybulloyevna, G. A. (2022, January). Factors affecting language learning process. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 277-279).
6. J. Cummins, Technology, literacy, and young second language learners: Designing educational futures, In L. L. Parker (Ed.), Technology-mediated learning environments for young English learners: Connections in and out of school, New York: Routledge, 2008, pp. 61–98
7. J. Kim, D. Craig, Validation of a videoconferenced speaking test. Computer Assisted Language Learning 25 (2012) 257
8. M. Levy, Technologies in use for second language learning. The Modern Language J., 93 (2009) 769–782
9. M.H. Long, The role of linguistic environment in second language acquisition, In Handbook of second language acquisition vol. 2, eds. W. Ritchie and T. Bhatia, San Diego, CA: Academic Press, 1996, 413–478
10. Presentations of Specialized Topics as a Ways of Testing Communication Skills, In: Testing Language Competence of Tertiary Students in LSP Courses, Hradec Králové: TAH reklamní agentura, ISBN 9788026065203, 2014, pp. 8-15
11. S. Katz, Videoconferencing with the French-speaking world: A user's guide. Foreign Language Annals, 34 (2001) 152–157
12. Y. Lee, Fostering second language oral communication through constructivist interaction in desktop videoconferencing, Foreign Language Annals, 40 (2007) 635–649
13. Rasulov Zubaydullo Izomovich. (2022). On the Basis of Information-Discursive Analysis. Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies, 18. <https://doi.org/10.21070/ijins.v18i.621>
14. Rasulov , Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 42(42).
извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/10944

15. Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(6), 35-40.
16. Rasulov , Z. (2023). Принцип когнитивной экономики как важный фактор в передаче информации. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 42(42). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/10954
17. Erkinovna, Y. F. . (2023). Four Current Approaches to Politeness. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 250–255. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/321>
18. Erkinovna , Y. F. . (2023). Grice’s Conversational Maxims in Our Everyday Life. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 151–154. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1118>
19. Erkinovna, Y. F. . (2023). Expression of the Modesty Maxim in English. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 333–336. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/338>
20. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2023). Cross-Cultural Variation and Distribution of Politeness Strategies . American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(8), 31–34. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/864>
21. Абдуллаева, Г. Г. (2022). COGNITIVE PERSPECTIVES OF TRAINING GOOD VOCABULARY LEARNERS. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ЯЗЫКА, ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, ПЕРЕВОДА, 3(1). <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/language/article/view/4566>
22. Abdullayeva, G. (2022). LEARNERS’PSYCHOLOGY AS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES INFLUENCING LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 11(11). http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/download/6321/4013
23. Abdullayeva, G. G. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 555-560. <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/520>
24. Abdullayeva, G. G. . (2023). Ways of Motivating Young Learners in EFL Classroom. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 122–124. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1109>
25. Абдуллаева, Г. Г. (2022). COGNITIVE PERSPECTIVES OF TRAINING GOOD VOCABULARY LEARNERS. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ЯЗЫКА,

ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, ПЕРЕВОДА, 3(1).

<https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/language/article/view/4566>

26. Abdullayeva, G. (2021). Sinxron tarjima san'atini egallash strategiyalari Annotatsiya. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 6(6).

http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/3032

27. Abdullayeva, G. (2021). Yosh tarjimonlarda sinxron tarjima qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish usullari. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 6(6).

http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/3037